

Complexes of Heterocyclic Ligands. Part-III: Complexes of Cobalt(II) with Antifuran- 2-carboxaldoxime

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THE use of oximes derived from aromatic aldehydes for complex formation is well reported in literature, but such heterocyclic aldehydes which contain one more additional donor atom *ortho* to the oxime linkage have been studied somewhat less frequently¹⁻⁴. The present study deals with the mode of bonding and the stereochemistry of some cobalt(II) complexes derived from antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime. The parent complex initially prepared is $[\text{Co}(\text{OX})_3]\text{Cl}_2$. Many other complexes have been prepared from this by the use of anion and by ligand replacements. The complexes have been characterised by analytical, molar conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data and octahedral structures have been proposed for them.

Experimental

The ligand antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime has been prepared by treating stoichiometric amounts of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, sodium acetate trihydrate and freshly distilled furan-2-carboxaldehyde in methanol. The crude oxime was recrystallised from methanol and had a melting point of 91°.

The parent complex $[\text{Co}(\text{OX})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ has been prepared by refluxing $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with three equi-

valents of oxime in methanol. This was recrystallised and analysed. A known weight of this complex was suspended in methanol and refluxed with calculated amount of the ligand or the sodium and ammonium salt of the desired anion in methanol for the replacement reactions. After the reaction is completed, as indicated by change in colour of the solution, the new complexes were obtained by repeated treatment with petroleum spirit. The type of complexes so obtained are shown in Chart 1.

Chart 1

The molecular formulae of all the complexes have been derived from the percentages of metal, C, H, N. The molar conductances have been measured in nitrobenzene at 10^{-8} M by using a Philips PR 9500 conductance instrument. These data are listed in Table 1. The infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded in an IR model 221 spectrometer while magnetic moments have been calculated by Gouy method. The electronic spectra have been recorded in the range 200-2000 nm with a Cary 14 recording spectrometer using nujol discs. These are listed in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

From the chart given above, it is seen that in the anion replacement reactions using thiocyanate,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA

Compd. No.	Formula	*Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)			Molar conductance mhos
		M	N	Cl	
1.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_3]\text{Cl}_2$	11.788 (12.73)	9.27 (9.06)	16.11 (15.31)	32.65
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{SCN})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.788 (12.55)	11.20 (11.93)	—	0.85
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{GN})_2]$	17.09 (17.69)	17.20 (16.8)	—	0.75
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.78 (13.23)	12.02 (12.58)	—	0.628
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]$	17.68 (15.97)	8.62 (7.59)	—	0.82
6.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$	12.87 (11.41)	13.90 (13.56)	—	32.65
7.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.78 (10.79)	10.46 (10.26)	11.947 (12.98)	32.85
8.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_5)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.788 (13.15)	13.05 (12.50)	14.89 (15.83)	36.85
9.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10.84 (12.73)	12.05 (12.10)	16.31 (15.31)	31.95
10.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	8.07 (10.82)	10.46 (10.29)	11.947 (13.03)	34.82
11.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	8.07 (10.87)	9.28 (9.86)	12.76 (12.48)	37.20

* All complexes gave consistent C and H analysis.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex no.	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν_1 kK	ν_2 kK	ν_3 kK	Calcd. ν	Dq cm^{-1}	B cm^{-1}
1.	5.18	7.15	14.34	21.83 17.54	15.51	836	871
2.	5.20	7.10	13.79	21.65 17.54	15.61	842	877
3.	5.08	7.068	13.89	22.22 17.70	15.94	827	861
4.	5.13	7.144	13.33	17.54 15.38	15.50	836	871
5.	4.49	7.219	13.02	17.39 16.00	15.67	845	883
6.	5.39	7.246	13.19	22.73 17.54	15.72	848	883
7.	4.95	7.147	14.08	22.22 17.54	15.51	836	871
8.	5.12	7.092	13.33	21.74 17.54	15.39	830	864
9.	4.85	7.042	14.08	17.39	15.28	824	858
10.	5.26	7.119	14.28	17.54	15.45	833	868
11.	5.25	7.053	13.33	17.24	15.31	825	860

cyanide, oxalate and nitrite* ions, replacement of two chloride ions occurs along with one mole of oxime and hence these anions appear to be coordinated to the metal(II). This is confirmed further from the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The use of nitrate ions on the other hand simply leads to the replacement of the two chloride ions while the coordination sphere remains intact. In all the ligand replacement reactions using different neutral ligands, only one mole of oxime is replaced, the other two as well as the chloride ions remain intact as shown by the electrolytic nature of these complexes.

The ligand antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime has the structure and is, therefore, capable of attaching

itself to a metal ion in three different ways. The nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the oxime moiety are very good donors and evidences for coordination through both are available. In the complexes being reported here, the ligand is found to behave as a bidentate ligand and the site of its coordination is indicated by the infrared data.

In the ir spectra of free ligand two bands appear at 3160 and 3040 cm^{-1} assigned to the intramolecularly bonded OH group. In the complexes, however, one strong peak appears at 3260 cm^{-1} showing that the hydrogen bonding has broken down as a result of complexation⁵⁻⁶. The sharp bands in the spectra of complexes at 670 and 500 cm^{-1} are absent from the spectra of free ligands and these

* Note—Ammonium nitrite used was taken out from a freshly sealed bottle. The compound is susceptible to decomposition and presence of nitrite ions in the salt was tested qualitatively prior to use.

are, therefore, assigned to be due to M-O (oxime) and M-O (furan ring) stretches indicating that the oxime is coordinated through both its oxygen atoms, one belonging to the oxime linkage and other to the furan ring. An outcome of this mode of coordination is an increase in the electron density as well as the ν_{CN} - stretching frequency, which occurs in free ligand at 1640 cm^{-1} and in the complexes at 1658 cm^{-1} . The nitrogen coordination imparts an reverse effect⁷⁻¹¹. The coordination of other ligands is indicated by the shifts in the position of relevant infrared bands as discussed elsewhere¹²⁻¹⁶.

The magnetic moments of the complexes are in the range 4.49-5.39 B.M. and correspond to a high spin configuration. In the electronic spectra, the three bands ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 are seen at 7.00, 14.00 and 21.00 kK. The positions of these bands suggest an octahedral structure for the complexes.

It is further seen that the ν_2 band is not observed as a single component, but is split into two definite components at 21.83 and 17.34 kK. The splitting of the band is an outcome of the lowering of octahedral symmetry due to the presence of a mixed ligand field around the metal.

The values of Dq and B have been calculated by using Figgis¹⁷ equations and lie around 850 and 875 cm^{-1} , respectively. Using these values the ν_2 transition is expected to lie at 15.00 kK. In most of the complexes a very weak band appears around 14.00 kK which is assigned to be the ν_2 transition. This is the weakest of all the three transitions since it involves the transition of an electron from the ${}^4T_{1g}$ state ($t_{2g}^6 e_g^2$) to ${}^4A_{2g}$ state ($t_{2g}^3 e_g^4$) and is hence a two electron process. It may further be stated that in the mixed ligand complexes reported here the Dq and B values should only be treated as approximate and should be used only for comparative purposes. However, these values are accurate enough to assign pseudo octahedral structures to the complexes.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of bis(Thenoyl Trifluoro Acetonato) and bis(Pivaloyl Trifluoro Acetonato) Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Heterocyclic Nitrogen Bases

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CHEMISTRY of metal β -diketonates has invoked lots of interest¹ in recent years in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extraction, column and thin layer chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in polymerisation reactions. Bis(β -diketonato) metal(II) complexes behave as Lewis acids and form five or six coordinate adducts with neutral donor molecule². The stability of an adduct depends both on the basicity of the β -diketonates and that of a neutral ligand. Introduction of an electron withdrawing group such as CF₃ into β -diketone increases the affinity of a central metal ion for ligation³. Formation of adducts of metal β -diketone chelates plays an important role in the synergistic enhancement of solvent extraction of metal ions^{4,5}. The quasi aromatic character of such compounds has also received considerable attention. Earlier, we reported⁶⁻⁹ many five coordinated nitrogen base adducts of copper(II) and zinc(II) β -diketonates and also the adducts^{10,11} of γ -substituted copper(II) β -diketonates. This communication reports the mixed ligand complexes of the type M(tta)₂B and M(pta)₂B where M = Cu(II), Zn(II); B is a nitrogen base and tta and pta are the anions of thenoyltrifluoroacetone and pivaloyltrifluoro acetone, respectively.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metal chelates were prepared by reacting aqueous solutions of the respective metal acetates with ethanol solution of the β -diketonates in 1 : 2 proportion. The chelates were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

Base adducts of zinc were prepared by refluxing the β -diketonates with the nitrogen bases (1 : 2) in methanol for 30 min and cooling the resulting solution overnight. Adducts of copper(II) β -diketonates

were prepared by warming the β -diketonates in excess of base in presence of small amount of chloroform and cooling the solution overnight in a refrigerator. The compounds were dried in vacuum.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M acetone solution of the complexes by Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic moments were measured on solid specimens at 25° by Guoy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 621 and 337 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were measured in 10⁻³ M (chloroform+base) solution using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compounds	Conduc- tance mhos.cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis%: Found(Calcd.)	
			metal	nitrogen
1. CuL ₂ Q	9.5	1.79	9.63 (10.0)	1.98 (2.21)
2. CuL ₂ (IQ)	8.8	1.80	9.72 (10.0)	1.95 (2.21)
3. CuL ₂ (pip)	8.5	1.78	10.52 (10.75)	1.98 (2.37)
4. CuL ₂ (Morph)	7.8	1.78	10.58 (10.79)	2.02 (2.38)
5. CuL ₂ (Quin)	11.2	1.82	9.45 (9.79)	1.81 (2.16)
6. ZnL ₂ Q	10.6	—	9.86 (10.26)	1.83 (2.20)
7. ZnL ₂ (IQ)	10.5	—	9.88 (10.26)	1.85 (2.20)
8. ZnL ₂ (pip)	11.8	—	10.85 (11.03)	2.01 (2.36)
9. ZnL ₂ (Morph)	12.4	—	10.82 (11.07)	2.02 (2.37)
10. ZnL ₂ (Quin)	8.9	—	9.75 (10.05)	1.91 (2.15)
11. CuL' ₂ Q	8.8	1.82	10.72 (10.90)	2.28 (2.40)
12. CuL' ₂ (IQ)	7.8	1.81	10.68 (10.90)	2.25 (2.40)
13. CuL' ₂ (pip)	9.5	1.79	11.45 (11.78)	2.30 (2.60)
14. CuL' ₂ (Morph)	9.8	1.80	11.61 (11.84)	2.32 (2.61)
15. CuL' ₂ (Quin)	10.1	1.79	10.32 (10.65)	2.05 (2.35)
16. ZnL' ₂ Q	10.4	—	10.85 (11.18)	2.01 (2.39)
17. ZnL' ₂ (IQ)	11.3	—	10.78 (11.18)	1.98 (2.39)
18. ZnL' ₂ (pip)	11.5	—	11.76 (12.09)	2.38 (2.59)
19. ZnL' ₂ (Morph)	8.9	—	11.78 (12.14)	2.34 (2.60)
20. ZnL' ₂ (Quin)	8.5	—	10.61 (10.92)	2.05 (2.34)

L = anion of thenoyltrifluoroacetone.

L' = anion of pivaloyltrifluoroacetone.

Q = quinoline, IQ = Isoquinoline, pip = piperidine,

Morph = Morpholine, Quin = Quinaldine.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the general formula M(tta)₂B or M(pta)₂B.